

Research Partnerships between Academic Librarians and Faculty Members: Perspectives on Knowledge Sharing and Collaboration

Talatu Rabassa¹

Ibrahim Wada²

Antonia Joel³

^{1,2,3} Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State-Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigated research partnerships and knowledge-sharing activities between academic librarians and faculty members at the University of Maiduguri, Borno State.

Methodology: A qualitative approach, utilizing Focus Group Discussions (FGD) as the primary data collection method, was employed to gather in-depth opinions from participants engaged in research and knowledge-sharing within the institution. The study's objectives focused on examining the nature of research partnerships and identifying the knowledge-sharing practices between librarians and faculty members. A purposive sampling method selected seven participants (three librarians and four faculty members) actively involved in institutional research and information exchange. Semi-structured interview questions aligned with these objectives were administered in English, allowing participants to freely express their perspectives. In adherence to ethical guidelines, permission was obtained from university management, and consent was secured from all participants. Audio recordings of the discussions were transcribed and analyzed thematically, uncovering key patterns in research and knowledge-sharing practices.

Findings/Results: Findings reveal that structured workshops and informal exchanges significantly enhance research skills, trust, and collaborative academic culture.

Conclusion: The study concludes that structured workshops and informal exchanges significantly enhance research skills, trust, and collaborative academic culture.

Recommendations: The study recommended that expanding interactive training and fostering informal meetups would further support discipline-specific knowledge exchange and collaborative problem-solving.

Keyword: Research Partnerships, Academic Librarians, Faculty Members, Perspectives, Knowledge Sharing, Collaboration

Introduction

Research partnerships and knowledge sharing are collaborative frameworks where academic professionals, including faculty members and librarians, work together to advance scholarly goals, resource access, and information literacy. By pooling expertise, these partnerships

enhance the depth and impact of academic research, curriculum development, and student learning outcomes. Knowledge sharing, a critical component of these partnerships, involves the reciprocal exchange of information, skills, and resources, fostering a culture of continuous learning and innovation within academic institutions.

This collaborative model not only bridges disciplinary boundaries but also supports inclusive scholarship, benefiting both under-resourced groups and diverse academic fields. Studies have shown that such partnerships promote engaged scholarship by connecting academic research with practical, real-world applications, improving the relevance, accessibility, and societal impact of scholarly work (Hynie et al., 2014; Buick et al., 2015). Additionally, partnerships between librarians and faculty enhance resource management and instructional design, contributing to a well-rounded academic environment that supports both research and teaching objectives. When effectively implemented, research partnerships and knowledge sharing foster a dynamic, resource-rich educational landscape, ultimately driving academic progress and innovation.

Research partnerships between academic librarians and faculty members are increasingly recognized for promoting equity, engaged scholarship, and interdisciplinary collaboration. Such partnerships enhance access to academic resources and strengthen research by merging diverse expertise. Hynie et al. (2014) explore partnerships that support underrepresented groups, such as refugee scholars, by improving equitable access to resources and fostering networked knowledge sharing. This approach aligns with the inclusive mission of academic institutions and is particularly impactful in resource-limited settings, where interdisciplinary collaboration enhances both the relevance and accessibility of research.

Similarly, Buick et al. (2015) emphasize the importance of co-production in research partnerships, where both librarians and faculty members collaboratively identify research problems, develop methodologies, and produce applicable findings. This practitioner-scholar model enriches research by incorporating both academic and practical perspectives, ensuring that findings are applicable beyond academia. It strengthens the collaborative nature of academic research, making outcomes more socially relevant and impactful.

Flierl et al. (2019) highlight the growing role of librarians as faculty developers, especially in information literacy and curriculum design. By engaging in curriculum development, librarians contribute significantly to student learning, supporting both knowledge acquisition and skill development. This collaboration expands faculty instructional capacity, demonstrating the value of librarian-faculty partnerships in enhancing teaching effectiveness. Nadim et al. (2023) further extend the impact of research partnerships by exploring community collaboration. They describe the San Antonio Research Partnership Portal, which connects academic researchers with community stakeholders, including government agencies and industries, to address societal issues. Such partnerships expand the societal reach of academic research and help

academic institutions address local and global challenges, thereby demonstrating academia's role in societal progress.

The need for such collaboration is evident in Ashilungu and Onyancha's (2023) examination of faculty-librarian cooperation in resource collection development at the University of Namibia. Their study finds that cooperative efforts, especially around digital resources, enhance the quality and accessibility of library materials. Librarians' expertise in resource management combined with faculty members' disciplinary knowledge creates a resource-rich library environment that supports both teaching and research. This approach underscores the need for partnerships to ensure library resources meet academic needs effectively, particularly as libraries transition to digital formats that require specialized selection and management skills.

Hadar et al. (2024) introduce the concept of Research-Practice Partnerships (RPPs), collaborations aimed at integrating theory and practice to produce practical, adaptable research. In the context of education, RPPs facilitate alignment between research and institutional goals, contributing to improved teaching practices. Hadar et al. (2024) describe RPPs as dynamic, with flexible roles that respond to the evolving needs of partnerships and institutions. This flexibility promotes shared ownership and mutual benefit, with participants contributing unique expertise to solve practical challenges. Such partnerships foster a situated model of collaboration, where librarians and faculty co-create solutions that enhance educational experiences.

Expanding on the relevance of RPPs, Toomarian et al. (2024) explore their role in educational neuroscience, where collaboration between researchers and practitioners leads to findings directly applicable in educational settings. By translating theoretical insights into practical applications, such partnerships bridge research and practice, ensuring that academic insights contribute meaningfully to educational environments. This collaboration enriches teaching and learning, reinforcing the mutual benefits of academic partnerships. Fadehan (2024) further examines librarian-faculty collaborations in Nigerian universities, noting that such partnerships are essential for aligning library resources with institutional goals. Effective collaboration between librarians and faculty members enhances information accessibility, supporting both teaching and research objectives and creating a supportive, resource-oriented academic environment.

Despite these benefits, challenges such as role ambiguity and power imbalances can hinder effective collaboration. Fadehan (2024) and Ashilungu and Onyancha (2023) observe that unclear roles and unequal authority create a perception of exclusivity, limiting the potential of partnerships. In practice, this exclusivity restricts the integration of librarians into the research process, creating a gap between academic support and practical research needs. In some institutions, including the University of Maiduguri, strained relationships between librarians

and faculty members are likely to diminish the collaborative impact of these partnerships, as seen in studies by Ashilungu and Onyancha (2023) and Fadehan (2024). These barriers emphasize the need for clear role definitions and equitable authority structures to foster effective and inclusive partnerships.

Ideally, collaborations between faculty and librarians would foster effective research support, knowledge sharing, and resource access. However, role ambiguity, power imbalances, and a lack of mutual understanding often hinder these partnerships, limiting their potential impact on academic progress. This issue significantly affects both librarians and faculty members, who depend on coordinated efforts to meet institutional and student needs. Despite growing recognition of the importance of these partnerships, there is a lack of empirical evidence on best practices for fostering productive, equitable relationships in academia. Moreover, increasing calls within the academic community highlight the need for a stronger, more collaborative relationship between librarians and faculty. This study is necessary to address these gaps, to provide strategies to enhance faculty-librarian partnerships for improved academic outcomes.

Objectives of the Study

- 1. Examine research partnership activities among academic librarians and faculty members
2. Determine knowledge sharing activities among academic librarians and faculty members

Literature Review

Research partnerships between academic librarians and faculty members have become pivotal to the success of higher education institutions. These collaborations extend beyond the traditional roles of librarians, incorporating them into key areas such as research processes, pedagogical design, and resource management. Various studies provide explanation on the nature and outcomes of these partnerships, emphasizing their impact on academic practices.

Figure 1: Collaborative Effort in Research

Librarians play a crucial role in enhancing information literacy and academic success through collaborative efforts with faculty, as highlighted by several studies. Näverå and Olsson (2022) illustrate how librarians actively engage in co-planning and co-teaching information literacy sessions within structured academic programmes, emphasizing the importance of continuous communication between librarians and faculty to improve students' research skills. This integration from the outset of academic programmes fosters students' development by enhancing their research competencies. Similarly, Reed, Kinder, and Farnum (2022) underscore the mutual benefits of librarian-faculty partnerships, where librarians gain insights into faculty expectations, allowing them to tailor instructional support effectively. This collaboration not only enriches the educational experience but also contributes significantly to student success.

Beyond instructional support, librarians also assist faculty throughout the academic publishing process, as demonstrated by Tulley and Balduff (2022) and Perez-Stable et al. (2020). Their research indicates that librarians provide essential support during research, writing, and publication stages, addressing scholarly communication issues such as authors' rights.

This is particularly beneficial for tenure-track faculty who depend on publishing for career advancement. Waterhouse (2023) further emphasizes the role of librarians in facilitating research activities through collaborative services that enhance access to resources and foster academic inquiry. Forbes (2022) expands this perspective by highlighting how librarians promote community engagement within research projects, thereby increasing the relevance and practical application of academic research. Together, these studies reinforce the notion that librarian-faculty collaborations are vital for improving educational outcomes and supporting faculty in their scholarly endeavours.

Kotur (2024) focuses on the interdisciplinary aspects of librarian-faculty collaboration, emphasizing how librarians facilitate connections across disciplines, manage research resources, and provide expertise in citation management and literature reviews. This study shows how librarians serve as central figures within research networks, ensuring that faculty have the necessary tools and support to succeed in interdisciplinary research.

Studies reveal that librarian-faculty partnerships are essential in supporting academic processes, though each emphasizes different aspects of collaboration. Näverå and Olsson (2022) focus on structurally integrating librarians into curricula for teaching information literacy, while Reed et al. (2022) highlight the adaptable nature of these partnerships across instructional contexts. In academic publishing, Tulley and Balduff (2022) describe how librarians support faculty through the entire publishing lifecycle, whereas Perez-Stable et al. (2020) find that collaboration depth varies based on faculty experience. Librarians' roles extend beyond campus boundaries as well; while Waterhouse (2023) examines internal partnerships

that enhance research practices, Forbes (2022) expands this scope by discussing how community engagement helps make research socially relevant.

Figure 2: Dimension of Interdisciplinary Research

Librarians also facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, especially in complex research projects spanning multiple fields, as Kotur (2024) highlights. This finding complements Tulley and Balduff's (2022) view of librarians as resource managers who streamline research processes. Together, these studies show that librarian-faculty partnerships now encompass teaching, publishing, interdisciplinary research, and community engagement, consistently enhancing academic outcomes. With faculty increasingly recognizing the value of these partnerships, the role of librarians in higher education is likely to grow, advancing both teaching and research quality.

Knowledge Sharing Activities among Academic Librarians and Faculty Members

In the academic environment, the collaboration between librarians and faculty members is crucial for the advancement of knowledge and the support of student learning. Librarians possess specialized skills in information management, research methodologies, and resource accessibility, while faculty members bring subject-specific expertise and pedagogical strategies. Together, they can create a synergistic relationship that enhances the educational landscape.

Several studies, such as Tan (2015), Tran (2022), Aziz, *et al.*, (2022), Bamigbola (2023), and Fan and Beh (2024) have examined the dynamics, strategies, and barriers to effective knowledge sharing in these contexts, contributing to an understanding of how to enhance collaborative efforts. Barry, Barrie, and Kuyateh (2024) investigated knowledge-sharing

practices among academic librarians in Malaysian libraries. Their study highlights that collaborative projects, information dissemination, and user training are key activities where knowledge sharing is crucial. The research emphasizes the role of intention, attitude, and subjective norms in influencing how librarians engage in knowledge-sharing activities, suggesting that a positive attitude toward sharing enhances collaboration with faculty members. The study also notes that these practices ultimately improve staff satisfaction and contribute to academic success.

Figure 3: Knowledge Sharing

Ahmed, Barry, and Noor (2022) identify key factors influencing knowledge-sharing practices among librarians in Malaysian academic libraries, highlighting the importance of collaboration with faculty members. They argue that trust, organizational culture, and clear communication channels are crucial in fostering knowledge exchange, with trust playing a central role in building confidence in each other's expertise and intentions. This study underlines that both formal and informal communication are vital for productive collaboration, allowing librarians and faculty members to share insights that enhance academic support and resource development.

Despite these potential benefits, significant barriers to knowledge sharing persist. At Delta State University, Izu and Fombad (2024) observe challenges such as a lack of supportive culture, motivation, technological resources, and interpersonal dynamics that inhibit collaborative efforts. They emphasize the need for a more conducive environment, where institutional support can drive stronger librarian-faculty connections through improved

technological infrastructure and encouragement of interpersonal relationships. Similarly, Muhammad's (2024) research in Katsina State universities highlights limited engagement between librarians and faculty due to inadequate resources and awareness of collaboration's benefits. His findings suggest that strategies like seminars and workshops could effectively promote structured, intentional knowledge-sharing opportunities within academic institutions.

Khalil and Khalil (2023) explore how knowledge sharing enhances service innovation within academic libraries, arguing that collaborative exchanges between librarians and faculty foster the development of new teaching and research methods. Extending this, Khalil, Khalil, and Khalil (2024) examine how management and IT innovations can mediate the relationship between knowledge sharing and innovation, asserting that effective institutional support strengthens collaborative practices. Their findings align with Ahmed and Barry (2023), who note that intention, attitude, and open organizational policies enhance knowledge sharing. These studies collectively highlight that while organizational culture, leadership, and communication are foundational to effective collaboration, structured support and technological resources are essential in overcoming barriers to a more integrated academic partnership.

Methodology

This study investigates knowledge sharing and research partnership activities between academic librarians and faculty members. A qualitative research design was employed, utilizing Focus Group Discussions (FGD) as the primary method for data collection. This approach was chosen to facilitate in-depth discussions and gather detailed insights into the experiences of participants. The study aimed to achieve two main objectives: first, to examine research partnership activities between academic librarians and faculty members, and second, to determine the knowledge-sharing activities occurring between these groups.

The population for this study included academic librarians and faculty members from selected University of Maiduguri, Borno State. A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants who were actively engaged in research and knowledge-sharing initiatives within the institution. A total of 7 participants, comprising 3 academic librarians and 4 faculty members, were chosen to participate in the study. The semi-structured interview format, conducted through FGDs, allowed participants to share their perspectives in a structured yet open-ended manner. The interview questions, developed in alignment with the study's objectives, were administered in English.

Prior to the commencement of the FGDs, permission was obtained from university management, and a consent letter was distributed to all participants, ensuring voluntary participation. During the FGDs, participants were encouraged to openly express their views without any interruptions. The discussions were audio-recorded to ensure accuracy in data collection, and the recordings were later transcribed into text for analysis.

The data gathered from the FGDs were analyzed using thematic analysis, which involved identifying recurring patterns or themes related to research partnerships and knowledge-sharing activities. The transcribed data were carefully reviewed and coded to extract key themes that informed the study's findings. This method ensured a rigorous and systematic approach to analyzing the qualitative data, providing a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between academic librarians and faculty members in the context of research and knowledge sharing.

Table 1: The Sample included the following faculty members:

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Qualification</i>	<i>Faculty/Department</i>
1	FM 1	Male	52	PhD	Librarian
2	FM 2	Male	50	PhD	Librarian
3	FM 3	Female	48	PhD	Management Science
4	FM 4	Male	49	PhD	Social Sciences
5	FM 5	Male	44	PhD	Librarian
6	FM 6	Male	53	PhD	Education
7	FM 7	Female	51	PhD	Education

This purposive sample captures diverse perspectives from faculty members across departments who have experience working with or engaging in research alongside academic librarians.

Focus Group Discussion Questions

Research Partnership

- Can you describe any collaborative research projects you've been involved in with academic librarians? What were the primary goals and outcomes of these projects?*
- How do librarians and faculty members typically contribute to these collaborative projects? Could you give examples of the specific roles or expertise each group brings?*
- In what ways have these partnerships improved the quality or scope of research outputs?*

Knowledge Sharing

- Can you tell me about any workshops or training sessions you've attended that were organized by the library? What topics were covered, and how useful were they?*
- How do these sessions contribute to knowledge sharing between faculty and librarians? Are there ways you think these could be improved?*
- Have you had opportunities to provide feedback during these sessions? If so, how has this influenced the library's offerings?*

Informal Knowledge Exchange

- a. Besides formal workshops, do you engage in informal discussions with librarians? Where and how do these exchanges usually take place?
- b. What kinds of topics are typically discussed in these informal settings? How do these discussions benefit your research work?
- c. How do these informal interactions impact your perception of librarians as research collaborators?

Results of the Focus Group Discussions

Participant 1: FM 1, Male, Age 52, PhD, Librarian: *FM 1 collaborated with academic librarians on a project aimed at supporting faculty and students in writing research papers. The project's primary goal was to develop guides and resources that addressed common challenges in academic writing, particularly in organizing and citing sources. The collaboration resulted in improved research papers with better structure and citation accuracy. FM 1 contributed his expertise in information organization and referencing styles, while faculty members added subject-specific insights. This initiative streamlined the writing process, enabling researchers to focus on content quality, thereby raising the overall academic standard of submissions.*

Participant 2: FM 2, Male, Age 50, PhD, Librarian: *FM 2 participated in a collaborative project focused on enhancing academic writing skills through research workshops for graduate students. The workshops aimed to help students structure research articles, conduct literature reviews, and adhere to academic conventions in writing. The outcome was an increase in students' writing confidence and noticeable improvements in the quality of their submissions. FM 2 organized the workshops, providing expertise in literature review techniques and citation management, while faculty members shared field-specific writing requirements. These workshops empowered students to produce more professionally rigorous papers, thereby contributing to higher-quality research outputs.*

Participant 3: FM 3, Male, Age 48, PhD, Management Science: *FM 3 collaborated with librarians on a project to create a standardized template and writing guide for management research publications. The aim was to improve the clarity and consistency of research articles within the field of management science. The outcome was a widely adopted template and writing framework that simplified the publication process. FM 3 contributed his knowledge of management research structures, while librarians assisted with formatting, referencing, and adherence to journal guidelines. This initiative led to higher-quality publications with improved coherence and adherence to academic standards, making the research more impactful and accessible within the management field.*

Participant 4: FM 4, Male, Age 49, PhD, Social Sciences: *FM 4 worked with librarians on a project focused on documenting best practices for social science research writing. The project aimed to assist researchers in structuring arguments and integrating sources effectively. The outcomes included a comprehensive guide now used by students and researchers in the social sciences. FM 4 shared insights into social science methodologies and effective argumentation, while librarians helped organize resources for referencing and citation. This collaboration has significantly improved the structure and academic rigor of social science research, resulting in papers that present arguments more clearly and integrate sources more effectively.*

Participant 5: FM 5, Male, Age 44, PhD, Librarian: *FM 5 collaborated on a project to create an online platform with tools and resources aimed at improving academic writing in research. The goal was to help students overcome common writing challenges, particularly in thesis and dissertation writing. The project resulted in the development of writing aids such as templates, citation guides, and sample structures. FM 5 contributed his knowledge of digital tools and academic standards, while faculty provided discipline-specific examples of writing conventions. This platform has enabled students to write more effectively, producing better-organized and well-referenced theses and dissertations, elevating the overall quality of research outputs within the institution.*

Participant 6: FM 6, Male, Age 53, PhD, Education: *FM 6 collaborated with librarians on a research writing initiative focused on improving academic writing among education students, particularly in writing research proposals for novice researchers. The project led to an increase in successful research proposals and positive feedback from students. FM 6 shared expertise in educational research methodologies, while librarians provided guidance on proposal structure and APA formatting. This collaboration has resulted in better-prepared research proposals, allowing students to develop rigorous research projects that contribute significantly to the field of education.*

Participant 7: FM 7, Female, Age 51, PhD, Education: *FM 7 participated in a project aimed at assisting faculty members in publishing their research by creating guides on structuring and submitting research articles. The primary goal was to improve submission success rates for faculty publications. The outcomes included a detailed publication guide and increased faculty engagement in scholarly publishing. FM 7 provided expertise on education-related publication standards, while librarians supported by organizing the guides and offering technical assistance with journal formatting requirements. The project resulted in more polished submissions and increased publication rates, enhancing the visibility and impact of research in education.*

These responses highlight each participant's contributions to research writing-focused projects, showing how collaborative efforts between faculty and librarians have improved writing

quality, structure, and adherence to academic standards, ultimately leading to stronger research outputs across various fields.

Thematic Summary Table 1: Research Partnership

Theme	Participants Involved	Project Focus	Primary Goals	Outcomes	Roles and Contributions	Impact on Research Quality
Support for Research Writing Skills	FM 1, FM 2, FM 6	Research writing skills workshops	Improve organization and citation skills	Better-organized papers, improved writing skills	Librarians guided organization, faculty offered insights	Improved coherence and academic rigor
Writing Tools and Templates	FM 3, FM 5	Writing templates and guides	Standardize formats for research writing	Streamlined writing, accessible tools	Librarians provided formatting, faculty shared conventions	Enhanced structure and consistency
Research Proposal Assistance	FM 6	Support for research proposals	Guide proposal structure and methodologies	More successful proposals, higher satisfaction	Librarians gave APA guidance, faculty provided methodologies	More rigorous, well-prepared proposals
Publication and Submission Guidance	FM 7	Publication submission support	Increase publication success rates	Detailed guides, more faculty publications	Faculty contributed content, librarians assisted with formatting	Broader dissemination and research visibility
Resource Access and Repository Development	FM 1, FM 4, FM 3	Digital repositories for resources	Enhance access to academic materials	Digital repositories, interdisciplinary access	Librarians organized resources, faculty defined requirements	Broadened scope and resource accessibility

This table consolidates the key themes across participants, showcasing collaborative efforts in supporting research writing skills, providing structured tools and templates, assisting with research proposals, guiding publication submissions, and improving resource access. Each theme highlights contributions from both librarians and faculty, demonstrating their combined impact on enhancing the quality of research outputs.

Knowledge Sharing

Participant 1: FM 1, Male, Age 52, PhD, Librarian: FM 1 attended workshops on citation management and database navigation, finding them valuable for enhancing both faculty and student research quality. These sessions enabled knowledge sharing, allowing faculty to better understand library resources and best practices. His feedback on incorporating more advanced database techniques led to subsequent sessions covering specialized tools.

Participant 2: FM 2, Male, Age 50, PhD, Librarian: FM 2 participated in sessions focused on research proposal writing and academic integrity. He found these workshops insightful for understanding proposal writing and avoiding plagiarism. They fostered a collaborative environment where librarians could share expertise on citation ethics with faculty. FM 2 suggested including hands-on exercises, which were later integrated into future sessions.

Participant 3: FM 3, Male, Age 48, PhD, Management Science: FM 3 attended training on EndNote and SPSS software, which he found useful for conducting data analysis in his research. The sessions promoted exchanges of research methodologies between librarians and faculty, enhancing his analytical capabilities. Based on his suggestion, the session durations were extended to allow more hands-on practice, a change that benefited the programme.

Participant 4: FM 4, Male, Age 49, PhD, Social Sciences: FM 4 engaged in workshops on digital tools for literature review, which streamlined his research process. These sessions provided an opportunity to connect with librarians and gain a better understanding of the resources in his field. His recommendation for interactive discussions on digital resources led to more engaging formats in future workshops.

Participant 5: FM 5, Male, Age 44, PhD, Librarian: FM 5 took part in workshops on academic writing techniques and citation management, viewing them as essential for staying current with research trends. The workshops fostered knowledge exchange between librarians and faculty, promoting mutual understanding. FM 5's feedback to include more interactive content led to improved engagement in subsequent sessions.

Participant 6: FM 6, Male, Age 53, PhD, Education: FM 6 attended training on academic writing and research methodology, which provided practical skills for his educational research. These sessions allowed librarians to share research strategies, facilitating collaborative learning. He recommended offering discipline-specific training, an idea that influenced the planning of future workshops to meet faculty needs better.

Participant 7: FM 7, Female, Age 51, PhD, Education: FM 7 participated in workshops on database management and digital research tools, which were instrumental in supporting her research. The sessions encouraged cross-disciplinary exchanges between faculty and

librarians. Her feedback to include more advanced topics was well received, resulting in additional specialized sessions that deepened the learning experience for participants.

Knowledge Sharing

Participant 1: FM 1, Male, Age 52, PhD, Librarian: *FM 1 regularly engaged in informal discussions with faculty in the library, focusing on research trends, citation methods, and new database resources. These interactions enhanced his view of faculty as collaborative partners, emphasizing the importance of mutual support in research.*

Participant 2: FM 2, Male, Age 50, PhD, Librarian: *FM 2 often had spontaneous exchanges with faculty on academic integrity and research ethics, specifically around citation ethics and research integrity. These interactions helped him see faculty as allies in promoting academic integrity, strengthening his collaborative approach to research support.*

Participant 3: FM 3, Male, Age 48, PhD, Management Science: *FM 3 frequently discussed software for data analysis and referencing with librarians on campus, including EndNote usage and data analysis techniques. This informal support encouraged him to view librarians as knowledgeable partners who positively impact his research productivity.*

Participant 4: FM 4, Male, Age 49, PhD, Social Sciences: *FM 4 often met librarians at the library café to discuss academic publishing and digital research tools. Topics included publishing guidelines and effective use of digital tools, which fostered trust and appreciation for librarians as collaborative resources in his research work.*

Participant 5: FM 5, Male, Age 34, PhD, Librarian: *FM 5 engaged in casual conversations with faculty about new academic trends, citation management, and academic publishing. These exchanges enhanced his perception of faculty as approachable and supportive, reinforcing a collaborative mindset in research.*

Participant 6: FM 6, Male, Age 53, PhD, Education: *FM 6 frequently interacted with librarians, discussing research methodology, publication processes, and data analysis strategies. These interactions fostered a sense of partnership, making him view librarians as indispensable collaborators in his research endeavors.*

Participant 7: FM 7, Female, Age 51, PhD, Education: *FM 7 often engaged in informal discussions with librarians about educational research tools, citation management, and research trends in education. These conversations reinforced her perception of librarians as valuable collaborators, strengthening trust and mutual respect in their partnership.*

Thematic Summary Table: Knowledge Sharing

Theme	Participants Involved	Workshops/Training Topics	Usefulness of Sessions	Knowledge Sharing and Feedback	Informal Knowledge Exchange Topics	Impact of Informal Interactions
Library-Organized Workshops	FM 1, FM 2, FM 4, FM 5, FM 7	Citation management, database use, proposal writing	Improved research and data management skills	Mutual learning, led to more advanced topics	Academic trends, citation, data organization	Enhanced trust, reinforced librarians' expertise
Training on Research Tools	FM 3, FM 6	EndNote, SPSS, academic writing	Practical application of research tools	Feedback shaped session structure and depth	Software tips, data analysis, referencing	Built rapport, encouraged collaborative research support
Knowledge Sharing and Feedback	All Participants	Session relevance, interactivity, content	Improved session responsiveness	Feedback led to longer, discipline-specific sessions	Field-specific needs, resource updates, publication tips	Fostered appreciation, strengthened academic collaboration
Informal Discussions	FM 1, FM 2, FM 3, FM 4, FM 5, FM 6	Research tools, referencing, publishing	Real-time problem-solving, tailored support	Suggested more informal meetups	Research trends, data management, software, methodologies	Strengthened trust and openness, collaborative relationships

This table organizes the workshop and training session experiences along with informal interactions, showing the impact of each on research quality, collaboration, and perceptions of librarians as research partners.

Discussion of the Findings

The collaboration between faculty members and librarians plays a critical role in advancing academic research quality and knowledge-sharing practices, particularly within university environments. Research on this topic demonstrates that faculty-librarian partnerships foster essential support systems for research activities, from improving research writing skills to enhancing resource accessibility and repository development. The findings of this study collaborate with Ashilungu and Onyancha (2023) where they highlight that faculty-librarian

cooperation is fundamental in electronic resource management, which enhances both access and usability of library resources, especially in academic settings with limited resources.

Sharing the same view, Fadehan (2024) reveals that while faculty and librarians often perceive their roles as mutually exclusive, their collaboration aligns their mission towards supporting institutional goals and ensuring efficient information services. Librarians contribute significantly to standardizing research formats and organizing academic materials, as seen in their work with digital repositories, which enable interdisciplinary access and ensure structured resource availability.

The findings agree with Kotur (2024) where the author disclose that academic librarians also support faculty in publication processes by providing guidance on formatting and submission, which Buick et al. (2015) suggest can increase the publication success rates by helping scholars meet journal-specific requirements. Importantly, initiatives such as research-writing skills workshops, where librarians focus on citation management and faculty on content structuring, have been found to improve the coherence and academic rigor of scholarly work. The findings also agree with Hadar et al., (2024) because they underscores that that intentional, role-based collaborations can bridge knowledge gaps, thus enhancing both research quality and the scope of knowledge sharing across university communities.

This study reveals that faculty-librarian workshops and informal discussions have shown substantial impact on fostering research skills, knowledge sharing, and collaborative relationships. In line with findings, Ashilungu & Onyancha, (2023) has pointed that library-organized workshops, attended by various faculty members, covered topics such as citation management, database use, and proposal writing, which proved highly beneficial in advancing research and data management skills. These sessions not only improved attendees' practical abilities but also facilitated mutual learning, with feedback from faculty guiding librarians toward more specialized topics in response to academic needs.

Workshops on research tools like EndNote and SPSS, targeting faculty such as pointed by FM 3 and FM 6, underscored the importance of practical tool application, with user feedback directly influencing the structure and depth of future sessions. This responsive approach not only allowed for the customization of content but also enhanced rapport between librarians and faculty, strengthening collaborative support.

Agreeing with the study by Kotur (2024), it is acknowledged that knowledge-sharing mechanisms are usually bolstered through feedback on session relevance and interactivity, which prompted the development of longer, discipline-specific workshops that addressed field-specific requirements, resource updates, and publication strategies. In the study carried out by Fadehan (2024) there is a coincidence of findings with this study where it is emphasised that informal discussions among faculty and librarians, especially around research tools, referencing, and publishing challenges, served as real-time problem-solving opportunities that

fostered a collaborative environment. These unstructured exchanges about academic trends, data management, and methodologies were instrumental in building trust and openness, reinforcing librarians' expertise and facilitating tailored research support. Together, these formal and informal interactions have not only enhanced skill development but also cultivated an academic culture of trust, openness, and ongoing knowledge exchange, thereby strengthening collaborative relationships (Buick et al., 2015; Hadar et al., 2024).

Conclusion

Faculty-librarian partnerships significantly enhance research skills, resource access, and knowledge sharing, fostering a collaborative academic culture. Both structured workshops and informal exchanges improve research outcomes, build trust, and support tailored academic needs.

Recommendations

The Librarians and faculty members should expand interactive training through develop regular, interactive workshops with various inputs to ensure relevance ideas that address discipline-specific needs.

The faculty members and the librarians should encourage informal meetups by facilitating regular informal knowledge-sharing sessions to build rapport, trust, and collaborative problem-solving in research.

References

- Ahmed, B., & Barry, M. (2023). A Preliminary Investigation into the Knowledge-Sharing Practices of Academic Librarians in Malaysia. *Research Journal of Library and Information Science*, 7(1), 24–39. Sryahwa Publications. <https://doi.org/10.22259/2637-5915.0701003>
- Ahmed, B., Noor, N. H. N. B. M., & Ahmed, M. (2022). Factors influencing knowledge sharing practices among librarians in the Malaysian academic libraries. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 48(6), 102612). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2022.102612>
- Ashilungu, M., & Onyancha, O. B. (2023). Faculty–librarian cooperation in collection development at the University of Namibia library, with special reference to electronic resources. *Collection and Curation*, 43(1), 8–18). Emerald. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cc-11-2022-0041>

- Aziz, N. E. A., Mokhtar, S. A., Arfin, N. A. M., Jamin, J., Aziz, W. A. H. W., & Abdullah, N. (2022). "The Successful Elements on Knowledge Sharing Constructed Social Media among Academic Staff". In International Academic Symposium of Social Science 2022 p. 66. MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2022082066>
- Bamigbola, A. (2023). Knowledge Sharing Patterns of Postgraduate Students. In Alternation Interdisciplinary Journal for the Study of the Arts and Humanities in Southern Africa (Vol. 13). University of KwaZulu-Natal. <https://doi.org/10.29086/978-0-9869937-4-9/2023/aasbs13/7>
- Barry, M., Barrie, A., & Kuyateh, A. (2024). Knowledge-Sharing Practice in Malaysian Academic Libraries: A Mediating Role of Intention. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development, Human Resources Management Academic Research Society*, 13, (3). (HRMARS). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarped/v13-i3/22066>
- Buick, F., Blackman, D., O'Flynn, J., O'Donnell, M., & West, D. (2015). Effective Practitioner–Scholar Relationships: Lessons from a Coproduction Partnership. *Public Administration Review*, 76(1), 35–47. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12481>
- Fadehan, F. (2024) The study reveals that faculty members and academic librarians perceive their relationship as mutually exclusive, yet collaboration is essential for mission alignment and effective information services.
- Fadehan, F. (2024). An Analysis of Library and Faculty Collaborations in South-West Universities in Nigeria. *Nigerian Libraries. Boldscholar*. <https://doi.org/10.61955/rpeyrf>
- Fan, Z., & Beh, L.S. (2024). Knowledge sharing among academics in higher education: A systematic literature review and future agenda. In *Educational Research Review*, 42, 100573). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2023.100573>
- Flierl, M., Maybe, C., & Fundator, R. (2019). Academic Librarians' Experiences as Faculty Developers: A Phenomenographic Study. In *Communications in Information Literacy*, 13(2). Portland State University Library. <https://doi.org/10.15760/comminfolit.2019.13.2.4>
- Forbes, C. (Ed.). (2022). *Academic Libraries and Collaborative Research Services*. Rowman & Littlefield Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.5771/9781538153703>
- Hadar, L. L., Baharav, H., & Cohen, E. (2024). Situated Partnership: Dynamics of Role Formation in a Research–Practice Partnership. In *Teachers College Record: The Voice*

of Scholarship in Education, 126(4-5), 88–113
. SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01614681241266396>

- Hynie, M., McGrath, S., Young, J. E. E., & Banerjee, P. (2014). Negotiations of engaged scholarship and equity through a global network of refugee scholars. *Scholarly and Research Communication*, CISP Journal Services 5(3.. <https://doi.org/10.22230/src.2014v5n3a151>
- Izu, L. O., & Fombad, M. C. (2024). Knowledge sharing strategies for improved service provision in the academic library at Delta State University Abraka Nigeria. In *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 30 (4), 320–344). Informa UK Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2024.2333536>
- Khalil, O., & Khalil, H. (2023). Knowledge Sharing and Service Innovation in Academic Libraries. In *European Conference on Knowledge Management* (Vol. 24, Issue 1, pp. 635–514). Academic Conferences International Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.34190/eckm.24.1.1359>
- Khalil, O., Khalil, H., & Khalil, N. (2024). Academic libraries' knowledge sharing and service innovation: The mediating role of management and IT innovations. In *The Journal of Academic Librarianship* (Vol. 50, Issue 1, p. 102832). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2023.102832>
- Kotur, M. (2024). Role of Librarian in Facilitating Research Collaboration: An Analysis. In *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4830333>
- Muhammad, M. (2024). Knowledge Sharing Practices in University Libraries in Katsina State, Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. In *Nigerian Libraries*. Boldscholar. <https://doi.org/10.61955/qryjzq>
- Nadim, M., Akopian, D., & Matamoros, A. (2023). San Antonio Research Partnership Portal: Evaluating keyword extraction tools to automate matchmaking for community research partnership. *Electronic Imaging* 35(3), 371–376. Society for Imaging Science & Technology. <https://doi.org/10.2352/ei.2023.35.3.mobmu-371>
- Näverå, E., & Olsson, A. K. (2022). Library-faculty collaboration in the light of a business administration bachelor's programme: 'The Scientific Wave.' *Nordic Journal of Information Literacy in Higher Education* 13(1), 39–55. University of Bergen Library. <https://doi.org/10.15845/noril.v13i1.3781>

- Perez-Stable, M. A., Arnold, J. M., Guth, L. F., & Meer, P. F. V. (2020). From Service Role to Partnership: Faculty Voices on Collaboration with Librarians. *portal: Libraries and the Academy* 20(1), 49–72. Project MUSE. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2020.0004>
- Reed, M. J., Kinder, D., & Farnum, C. (2022). Collaboration between Librarians and Teaching Faculty to Teach Information Literacy at one Ontario University: Experiences and Outcomes. *Ryerson University Library and Archives* 2022. <https://doi.org/10.32920/14639529.v1>
- Tan, C. N. L. (2015). Enhancing knowledge sharing and research collaboration among academics: the role of knowledge management. *Higher Education* 71(4), 525–556. Springer Science and Business Media LLC. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-015-9922-6>
- Toomarian, E. Y., Gosavi, R. S., Hasak, L., Bunderson, M., & McCandliss, B. (2024). Emerging Insights from a Research-Practice Partnership Approach to Educational Neuroscience. *Center for Open Science*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/xh74s>
- Tran, N. T. (2022). Literature Review on Knowledge Sharing among University Lecturers. *Cross Current International Journal of Economics, Management and Media Studies* 4(4), 43–50. SASPR Edu International Pvt. Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.36344/ccijemms.2022.v04i04.001>
- Tulley, C., & Balduff, D. (2022). Reevaluating and Strengthening Publishing Partnerships between Librarians and Researchers. *The Serials Librarian* 82(1–4), 72–76. Informa UK Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526x.2022.2018206>
- Waterhouse, J. (2023). Academic libraries and collaborative research services. *Journal of Electronic Resources Librarianship* 35(1), 81–82. Informa UK Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1941126x.2023.2165255>